

KEY INDICATORS

With 132,207 hectares in 2024, Croatia had 8.8% of its farmland under organic management, which was below the European Union average of 11.1% but above that of the EU-13 countries (7.4% in 2024). Like in many countries that became a member of the European Union in or after 2004, growth was exceptional, amounting to an increase of more than 1000 times in the 2001 to 2024 period, thus showing the highest area growth in the European Union. Retail sales data is not available for Croatia.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

114 ha (0%)

132,207 ha (8.8%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

115.871%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

N/D

43,673 ha (4.9%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

N/D

17,053 ha (21.6%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

N/D

71,481 ha (13.2%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

744 † (3.4%)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

12

6,211 (4.3%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

6

Processors

N/D

464

Importers

N/D

10

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

N/D

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

N/D

Imports

N/D

812 †

Source: FIBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN CROATIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat, Ministry of Agriculture, Nic Lampkin

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES GROWTH IN CROATIA

Source: Darko Znaor/Ecologica, no data updates since 2014

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Croatian CAP strategic plan foresees an almost doubling of the organic land area supported by 2027 compared with 2018, but with a reduction in total expenditure per ha of nearly 20%, due primarily to the removal of the 20% additional conversion support available in the previous period.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	94 kha	182 kha (+93%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	6.4 %	12.3% (+93%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	91%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	33 M€	51 M€ (+56%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	350 €	283 € (-19%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	238 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	468 M€	24.6%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	497 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	3,687 M€	6.4%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	310	348	577	868	868	868
	2023*	P2	157	235	480	1074	754	754
Change from 2019 to 2023			-49%	-32%	-17%	+24%	-13%	-13%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	258	290	481	723	723	723
	2023*	P2	157	235	480	1074	754	754
Change from 2019 to 2023			-39%	-19%	0%	+49%	+4%	+4%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		20%	20%	20%	20%	20%	20%
	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

*€60/ha extra for first 10 ha in conversion, 5 ha maintenance. Walnuts and hazelnuts €516/ha.

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Both Croatian action plans to date reflect Croatia's recent EU membership and the early stage of organic farming development, with capacity building in research, training, and advisory services as a priority. While the strategic targets are ambitious, there is room to broaden the scope and detail of the action plans to address specific needs.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET*	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2011-16	8% of UAA by 2016	30% annual growth in processing
Current Action Plan	2023-27	12% of UAA by 2027 (CSP)	N/D

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2011-2016)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023-2027)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Croatia is just over 1%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids and consumer information. However, organic aquaculture is not highlighted in the national OAP from 2030. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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